

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages

Final Thematic Best Practice Reports Deliverable 1.7

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main goal of this report (D1.7 Final Thematic Best Practice Reports) is to share the results of the last two Best Practice sessions that were held within the TransformAr consortium. Best Practice sessions are structured exchanges where project partners and stakeholders share experiences, methods, and lessons learned to highlight what works in practice and how it can be applied elsewhere. The first report is about “A Multi-Actor Approach to Governance” (the fifth session). The second report is about “Looking back on TransformAr and transformational adaptation” (the sixth and final session within the TransformAr project).

Session 5: A Multi-Actor Approach to Governance

The session about a Multi-Actor Approach to Governance took place on the 25th of November 2024. Unfortunately, not every demonstrator could participate, but we made the recording available for the people who could not participate, gathered their experiences and opinions and integrated them in this report. We had people participating from the following demonstrator areas: Egaleo, Galicia, Gjovik and Guadeloupe. The presentation of this session was taken care of by Feuga and the moderation and facilitation were done by Verhaert.

This session explored the key elements for effective governance. We discussed that successful governance and innovation require collaboration between many different groups. Small, focused coalitions (mini-coalitions) are especially powerful, as they bring together diverse expertise and resources. To achieve lasting success, we need to move away from short-term planning and focus on long-term commitments. This allows us to handle changes and create lasting solutions. A broad, systemic approach, including exploring different scenarios, building skills, and using local knowledge, is essential for creating adaptable and resilient systems. The innovation ecosystem dimensions were intended to create viable solutions. But, due to institutionalised behaviour and reliance on technical partners, the consultations and solution ownership workshops were merged. The goal was to identify "coalitions of the willing" that would ensure the demonstrator's continuity beyond the TransformAr project. It was found that scenario exploration and systems thinking counteract innovation inertia and enable transformative changes.

Incorporating local knowledge is invaluable for making solutions relevant and practical, as it reduces reliance on top-down methods. To ensure the sustainability of these co-creation activities, we prioritised capacity building through the introduction of monthly meetings. This transition from a reflective to a more systematic model will be detailed further in Deliverable 1.3, a report that outlines our approach to climate-resilient regional transformation strategies. Ultimately, a strong commitment to social resilience and sustainability, supported by targeted skill-building, is crucial for long-term governance success. "

Session 6: Looking back on TransformAr

The session about Looking back on TransformAr and transformational adaptation took place on the sixth of June 2025. I was designed as an interactive workshop, lasting roughly one and a half hours, with the goal of reflecting on the TransformAr projects and the concept of transformational adaptation. The

workshop was open to all consortium partners. There were participants attending from the following demonstrators: Galicia, Oristano, West Country Region, Egaleo and Gjovik.

The session was structured to gather collective insights on the TransformAr projects. A key component of the workshop was the use of a Mural board to capture input from participants. The discussion was divided into two main parts. The first part focused on a retrospective analysis of the TransformAr project, with participants asked to share what went well and what was difficult from their perspective. The second part introduced the transformational adaptation scorecard that was developed by the University of Antwerp. This scorecard served as a self-assessment tool to evaluate the transformative character of climate adaptation projects.

The workshop served as a valuable exercise in collective reflection, providing insights into both the successes and challenges of the TransformAr project. The session emphasised the importance of self-assessment and the use of tools like the scorecard to identify areas for improvement.

1.0 Best Practice Report on A Multi-Actor Approach to Governance

Within TransformAr, the Best Practices Sessions and Reports served as a key mechanism for sharing knowledge and improving the project's outcomes. The main goal of this initiative was to facilitate an exchange of experiences and best practices among the various demonstrator teams and other stakeholders. This helped the teams proactively address common challenges and avoid potential implementation hurdles.

Six facilitated sessions were held, each focused on a specific topic crucial to the project's success. These sessions covered a range of subjects, from stakeholder management and change management to technical topics like making data available and accessible. This structured approach ensured that the discussions were targeted and productive.

After the sessions, we compiled the insights and "tips & tricks" into three thematic best practice reports. Each report synthesised the learnings from two sessions. These reports, designated as D1.5 (stakeholder management & change management), D1.6 (How to make data available and accessible & developing transformational pathways), and D1.7 (A multi-actor approach to governance & looking back on TransformAr and transformational adaptation), served as a permanent record of the key takeaways. The final reports were then published online with valuable "learning stories," making the knowledge accessible to a wider audience both within and outside the project.

This entire process was a collaborative effort, with Verhaert coordinating the sessions and all demonstrators, technical partners, and the MOG actively contributing.

1.1 Introduction

In a rapidly changing world, effective governance is more important than ever. The challenges faced by different sectors, particularly agriculture, small businesses, and local communities, require innovative solutions that can only be achieved through collaboration. The multi-actor approach to governance emphasises the importance of involving a diverse range of stakeholders, from the public and private sectors to civil society. This approach is essential for creating sustainable, resilient systems that can address both short-term needs and long-term goals.

The session discussed in this report explored the complexities and opportunities of applying a multi-actor governance model. It highlighted the importance of engaging stakeholders who often face resource constraints, such as small enterprises and local communities, and emphasised the need for solutions that not only address immediate challenges but also contribute to long-term adaptation and transformation. Key insights from this session show that while the path to effective governance is filled with obstacles, the collective effort of multiple actors working together can bring about meaningful change.

This report will delve into the main discussions and outcomes of the session, focusing on how various actors, including local governments, small businesses, and citizens, can collaborate to foster sustainable governance systems. By examining examples, challenges, and lessons learned, we aim to provide actionable recommendations for enhancing multi-actor governance frameworks in practice.

1.2 How did we get here?

The global journey towards a multi-actor approach to governance has been shaped by a combination of evolving challenges, innovative ideas, and the growing recognition that traditional governance models are often inadequate in addressing complex, interconnected issues. In recent years, various sectors have been grappling with the need for more inclusive, flexible, and adaptive governance structures, particularly in response to climate change, economic instability, and social inequalities.

In recent years, various sectors have been grappling with the need for more inclusive, flexible, and adaptive governance structures, particularly in response to climate change, economic instability, and social inequalities. For example, many coastal cities are redesigning flood management systems by combining traditional infrastructure, such as dikes and seawalls, with nature-based solutions like wetlands restoration to better cope with rising sea levels.

Recognising artificial conditions for governance was a pivotal step in this transformation. These conditions weren't natural limitations; they were predetermined barriers, both technical and geographical, that often prevented genuine collaboration. Artificial conditions for governance are essentially limitations or obstacles embedded in older systems that prevent effective collaboration and adaptation. They create rigid, predefined pathways that hinder flexibility and stakeholder participation. Instead of allowing for organic, co-created solutions, these conditions lead to less effective, "business as usual" outcomes.

From a technical perspective, these conditions meant stakeholders couldn't easily work together or share information. The solution was the emergence of an interactive innovation broker, a role essential for bridging these gaps and fostering knowledge exchange. On a geographical level, artificial conditions led to solutions that were disconnected from local realities. To overcome this, it became vital to involve local partners, key stakeholders, and the broader regional community to ensure solutions truly addressed the needs on the ground.

Figure 1: Artificial conditions for Governance

As these governance structures matured, the focus shifted towards producing transversal exchanges, including sharing best practices and learning stories across regions. This focus on transversal knowledge exchange has proven essential in reaching beyond individual stakeholders. By engaging with over 30 activities involving more than 10 different stakeholders, we have been able to drive cross-sectoral learning and innovation, though not without its challenges.

However, the artificial conditions created in earlier governance models led to downgraded solutions and persistent bottlenecks in the system. These predetermined pathways often confined the scope for true adaptation, with many stakeholders resorting to "business as usual" when faced with trouble—

whether in identification, planning, implementation, or evaluation. This reluctance to change was a significant barrier.

To address these issues, a change of mindset was necessary. The move towards co-creation became central to the new governance model. Over time, collaborations began to snowball, resulting in the formation of a community of practice at the EU level. This shift was not just about technical solutions but also about empowering stakeholders and facilitating participation at multiple levels.

Figure 2: Multi-actor approach to governance - methodology

The framework, established in 2022 under **Deliverable D1.1: Stakeholder engagement guidelines**, marked a significant turning point. It introduced the concept of interactive innovation, structured around a three-level system:

1. **A level playing field**, ensuring that all participants, regardless of size, background, or resources, can contribute and benefit equally.
2. **A network of networks**, connecting multiple existing groups, organisations, or initiatives to share knowledge and create synergies.

Interactive innovation with stakeholder empowerment, fostering collaboration where stakeholders actively co-create solutions, guided and supported by facilitators inside and outside the consortium. This framework created a robust environment for continuous engagement and innovation across stakeholders.

Figure 3: Framework from 2022: Interactive Innovation

In 2023, a critical reassessment was made, which led to the development of a decision-making tool known as the Interactive Innovation Index. This tool helps evaluate the balance between learning, coalition-building, and the role of facilitators in guiding the process. The introduction of this tool has allowed us to better manage the dynamic relationships between different stakeholders and ensure that the governance process remains adaptable and inclusive.

By learning from past experiences, we have forged a path towards a more flexible, collaborative, and innovative governance model, one that is better equipped to address complex societal challenges and deliver long-term, sustainable solutions.

Figure 4: Interactive Innovation Index

1.3 Transforming systems

Transforming governance systems towards a multi-actor approach involves reshaping how we think about resources, collaboration, and long-term adaptation. This process goes beyond the technicalities of managing projects and extends into how governance structures evolve to meet the complex and dynamic challenges of sustainability.

What was lacking in 2023

By 2023, it became evident that key elements were missing from the governance approach, which hindered progress and innovation. One of the most significant gaps was the absence of a transversal assessment, a holistic evaluation that would consider the interconnections between sectors, stakeholders, and challenges. This limited the ability to understand the broader implications of decisions and failed to provide the necessary context for effective adaptation.

Moreover, there was insufficient resource prioritisation. The allocation of resources was often reactive and lacked alignment with long-term goals, which meant that responses to urgent issues often outpaced sustainable planning. This deficiency in long-term strategic thinking resulted in short-term expectations becoming the dominant focus, preventing the creation of lasting solutions for complex problems.

Additionally, there was a need for renewed coalitions to tackle new and emerging challenges. Existing partnerships were often too rigid, limiting their ability to adapt to the changing needs of the landscape. Social resilience was also an area of concern, as communities were often not sufficiently prepared or supported to face ongoing challenges.

The 2024 assessment: progress and challenges

As we entered 2024, it was clear that progress had been made, but significant challenges remained. Different approaches across demonstrators have emerged, each responding to the unique circumstances of their context. However, one common theme was the realisation that timeframes are too short to address the systemic changes needed.

The innovation ecosystem dimensions were meant to create viable solutions. However, institutionalised behaviour and artificial conditions created by this model of governance and its reliance on technical partners influenced the prioritisation of pathways towards the original portfolio of solutions. For instance, one demonstrator working on coastal adaptation faced difficulties in aligning municipal planning cycles with the longer-term needs of ecosystem restoration projects, which slowed down decision-making and limited stakeholder engagement.

There was also a noticeable absence of agents for a new governance matrix, people and organisations capable of bridging sectors, connecting actors, and facilitating the transitions that are needed. Capacity building remained far from ideal, as stakeholders still lack the tools, knowledge, and resources to fully participate in governance processes. Furthermore, many of the solutions proposed still followed top-down approaches, undermining the potential for collaborative, participatory governance. Finally, the lack of a systemic approach continued to pose a significant barrier to effective adaptation and transformation.

Transforming artificial conditions into high entropy systems

One of the key lessons learned from the past years is the need to move from artificial conditions—those that are artificially structured or limited by predefined pathways—towards a high-entropy system, characterised by flexibility, uncertainty, and the potential for innovation. This is achieved by embracing interactive innovation and facilitating an extended portfolio of initiatives. The goal is to orient resource allocation in ways that balance both horizontal and vertical approaches to governance.

Horizontal integration can be achieved through a levelled playing field, where a network of networks emerges, facilitating cross-sector and cross-regional collaboration. This interactive innovation approach allows for diverse voices to come together and co-create solutions in a more inclusive manner.

Vertical integration, on the other hand, requires a stronger focus on learning, balance, coalitions, and the role of facilitators. These elements ensure that innovation is not only encouraged but also continuously nurtured through long-term commitments and ongoing dialogue between stakeholders.

Table 1: Orienting the short-term future allocation of resources

	Levelled playing field	Network of networks	Interactive innovation
Learning	Tacit knowledge	Multiple roles	Knowledge pool
Balance	Methodology	Feedback	Initiative
Coalitions	Awareness	Champions	Commitment
Facilitators	Ambassadors	Assistance	Practitioners

Bringing tacit knowledge into the field

A key part of transforming governance systems is ensuring that tacit knowledge—the unspoken, experience-based knowledge held by local communities and stakeholders—is brought into the decision-making process. This is essential to avoid prioritizing technology over people-centered solutions.

Additionally, incorporating tacit knowledge helps to reduce duplication, proliferation, and information overload, all of which are common pitfalls when too many actors are involved but without clear coordination. Ensuring that knowledge flows smoothly between stakeholders, rather than becoming siloed, is critical for sustaining solutions and ensuring their relevance over time. The goal is to create long-lasting transformative adaptations that are not simply technical fixes but shifts in how communities and stakeholders approach governance itself.

Applying a systemic perspective

To navigate the challenges of transformation, a systemic perspective is essential. This involves:

- **Scenario exploration:** allowing stakeholders to envision multiple futures and plan accordingly, considering both risks and opportunities.
- **Systems thinking:** means looking at the relationships and interdependencies between all parts of a project together, rather than viewing each part in isolation. In this context, it helps to understand how the entrenched habits (innovation inertia) of the project are influenced by the entire system, so you can address the underlying causes and find more radical solutions.
- **Rearranging the system to uncover new coalitions and foster new partnerships:** ensuring that everyone has a stake in the process.
- **Granting alternatives that reduce governance liability:** creating more flexible, inclusive pathways for adaptation.
- **Encouraging agents who can play different roles:** whether as facilitators, innovators, or connectors, ensuring that governance is not limited to a few key players but is distributed across many stakeholders with diverse skills and knowledge.
- Finally, it is essential to **establish repetition and long-term commitment to the process.** This ensures that resolutions are not only reached but also sustained over time, incentivising innovation and facilitating its continuity.

By taking these steps, we move towards creating systems of governance that are not just reactive or short-term but resilient and adaptable in the face of ongoing change. The key is to make governance

more inclusive, dynamic, and capable of addressing complex challenges with long-lasting, transformative solutions.

1.4 Mini-coalitions

The concept of mini coalitions is central to the multi-actor approach to governance and plays a pivotal role in achieving transformative change within complex systems. Mini coalitions are smaller, more agile groups that emerge within the broader governance framework. These coalitions allow for a focused, flexible, and adaptive way of working, crucial when tackling specific challenges or goals that may not be addressed by larger, more traditional governing bodies.

In practice, mini coalitions often form organically as stakeholders with shared interests, experiences, and resources come together to work on specific issues. They are particularly valuable because they create opportunities for more targeted collaboration. By bringing together experts, community leaders, local stakeholders, and innovators from various sectors, be it public, private, or civil society, these coalitions can address niche problems that may be overlooked in broader policy-making circles.

Why mini coalitions?

Several factors make mini coalitions a compelling approach to governance. First, they are built around a shared agenda, where all members are aligned with common goals, enabling them to pool resources and expertise towards a specific outcome. This unity makes the coalition stronger and more focused on achieving its objectives. Furthermore, incentives for innovation are often built into the very fabric of these coalitions, encouraging participants to explore new ideas and approaches. By working together, stakeholders can overcome traditional barriers to innovation and create solutions that might not have emerged in more siloed environments.

Importantly, mini coalitions often form as coalitions of the willing, where individuals or organisations voluntarily come together because they share a vested interest in solving a particular problem. This self-selection ensures that participants are motivated, committed, and invested in the success of the initiative. The coalition members are typically pioneering solutions, ready to explore uncharted territory and take risks to test new approaches, which is essential for driving innovation and meaningful change.

Another significant advantage of mini coalitions is their ability to work beyond the four-year timeframe of projects like TransformAr and political and policy cycles. Unlike large institutions that may be bound by electoral cycles and short-term goals, mini coalitions can maintain continuity and focus on long-term solutions. This flexibility enables them to address issues that require sustained effort and commitment, such as climate change, social resilience, or systemic adaptation.

Mini coalitions also facilitate a more localised approach to problem-solving, allowing members to respond to context-specific needs. For instance, agricultural stakeholders may work closely with local communities to pilot sustainable practices, while other partners might focus on policy alignment at regional or national levels. This local engagement fosters ownership and commitment to the solutions being implemented, as stakeholders are directly involved in both the design and the execution of the initiatives.

Another significant advantage of mini coalitions is their ability to share best practices and leverage diverse expertise from within the coalition and across the wider network of stakeholders. By creating opportunities for cross-sector collaboration, mini coalitions are not only able to pilot solutions more effectively but also to identify innovative ideas that can be scaled up or adapted for use by larger governance structures. These exchanges can lead to transversal learning, where knowledge flows freely between different groups, resulting in more comprehensive and sustainable solutions. You can find lots of concrete examples of mini coalitions below in section 1.5.

A new matrix for governance

In the context of governance, mini coalitions also represent the potential for a new matrix of collaboration that can reshape how stakeholders interact and contribute to decision-making processes. This new matrix aims to expand the reach of governance by reaching out to missing stakeholders, ensuring that no key voices are left behind in the decision-making process. These stakeholders, who might have previously been excluded from traditional governance structures, are now integral to the design and implementation of policies and solutions.

An essential part of this new matrix is mapping the knowledge pool. By systematically identifying and categorising the expertise, resources, and experiences within the various coalitions, governance structures can become more effective in addressing complex challenges. The pooling of knowledge and resources fosters a more robust decision-making process, ensuring that solutions are well-informed and context-specific.

Additionally, this new approach moves beyond simply replicating solutions from one region or context to another. Instead, the focus is on capacity building, ensuring that stakeholders are empowered with the tools, knowledge, and skills they need to continue innovating and adapting solutions in their own territories. This shift promotes a more sustainable form of governance, where solutions are not just copied but adapted to fit local needs and realities, creating a more resilient system.

As part of the expansion of the new matrix, there is a key question: what territories are going to follow? With the success of mini coalitions in certain areas, there is the potential for scaling up and expanding this approach to other regions or sectors. The adaptability of mini coalitions allows this model to spread, with new stakeholders joining the process, forming new coalitions, and contributing to the governance landscape. This expansion contributes to the creation of a network of networks, fostering greater connectivity and collaboration across territories and sectors, and amplifying the impact of governance processes on a larger scale.

We need scenarios

To further strengthen the role of mini coalitions, we must recognise the importance of scenarios in governance. Developing tools and projections is critical to guiding coalitions in their efforts, helping them visualise potential outcomes and anticipate challenges. These tools provide a solid foundation for decision-making and enable stakeholders to act with foresight and confidence.

At the same time, it's crucial to push agents against the wall, creating a sense of urgency that drives action. This can be achieved by presenting stark realities, tough decisions, and challenges that need to be overcome. The idea is to foster a mindset where agents feel compelled to act, to innovate, and to commit.

In this context, the other legacy of mini coalitions lies in their ability to provide a wider portfolio of solutions and alternatives. Mini coalitions are uniquely positioned to offer a variety of approaches that can be tested and refined over time. This diversity of approaches provides resilience and ensures that solutions are adaptable to different contexts and needs.

Commitment within mini coalitions means not only sustaining momentum but also de-incentivising exit. Once stakeholders have committed to the coalition, they are less likely to walk away when challenges arise. Instead, they will be encouraged to stay and push through the difficulties, contributing to long-term success.

Finally, space and transparency are critical components for maintaining effective mini coalitions. As these coalitions evolve, it's essential to create an open environment where stakeholders can engage in honest conversations, share insights, and collaborate without barriers. By making space for this open dialogue and ensuring transparency, participants will build trust and a stronger sense of collective ownership. The statement "We are going to see each other" emphasises this commitment to shared visibility, interaction, and mutual accountability.

1.5 Examples from the demonstrators

Example 1: **Mini Coalitions and Innovation Incentives** - Guadeloupe

The importance of mini coalitions was emphasised during the session to develop a shared agenda focused on innovation incentives. One example of this is the collaboration between various stakeholders (local governments, the private sector, and civil society organisations) working on the sustainability of the agricultural sector in Guadeloupe. This initiative is a coalition of the willing, where they are developing pioneering solutions for local agricultural practices. The collaboration ensures that innovations are applied directly, even beyond the typical four-year political terms, and builds upon past experiences and best practices.

Example 2: **Interaction Between Public, Private, and Civil Sectors** - Egaleo & Guadeloupe

The interactive innovation process is a key concept for engaging different actors. During the session, it was discussed how collaboration between the three sectors – public, private, and civil sectors – led to more diverse perspectives in decision-making. One example of this is the co-creation of solutions to promote social resilience, where entrepreneurs, local governments, and NGOs collaborate to develop alternatives for social housing. By leveraging their different perspectives and resources, the coalition was able to find innovative solutions that not only address short-term needs but also focus on sustainable and long-term changes.

Example 3: **Scenarios and Long-Term Planning** - Gjovik

The session emphasised the development of scenarios for the future to enable systemic changes. Creating future projections and applying scenario exploration is essential for building robust and flexible systems. One example is a coalition focused on adapting infrastructure for climate resilience. They explored multiple scenarios, such as the potential impact of droughts or floods in the region, and developed strategies that would work across various possible future scenarios. This ensures that the coalition can adapt to uncertainties in the long term.

Example 4: **The Role of Tacit Knowledge and Reducing Duplication** – Gjovik & Galicia

A key point during the session was the idea of gathering and utilising tacit knowledge. This can help reduce duplication. One concrete example is a coalition of knowledge institutions and local entrepreneurs working on a more sustainable energy mix for a region. Members of this coalition bring their tacit knowledge into play, allowing them to develop practical, locally tailored solutions. This prevents them from getting stuck in technological solutions that aren't sustainable in the long term.

Example 5: **Creating Space for Continuous Innovation** – Galicia & Gjovik

The session discussed the importance of creating space and transparency for the continuity of innovation. This means that even when projects overlap and some stakeholders temporarily drop out, the foundation of the collaboration remains intact. One example is a coalition focused on the sustainability of the water sector. Here, transparency and long-term commitment were ensured by maintaining a sustainable network of partners who, regardless of political changes, continue their collaboration. This was made possible by a shared trust in the long-term interests of the project and the fact that resources and knowledge within the coalition are continuously shared and strengthened.

Example 6: **Innovation Through Horizontal and Vertical Interaction** - Guadeloupe

The idea of horizontal and vertical interaction was mentioned as a way to bring resources and knowledge across different layers of society. This could, for example, involve implementing interactive innovation techniques that engage both local stakeholders (such as farmers or small businesses) and larger organisations or governments. In a specific case, farmers could share knowledge about sustainable agricultural practices through their local networks, while policymakers could gather input on what works at the local level and translate this into policy adjustments at the regional or national level. This ensures an equitable distribution of resources and information, contributing to broader support for innovative solutions.

1.6 Co-creating regional governance visions: insights from the Mural exercises

In order to shape a shared vision for governance within each demonstrator region, we conducted an exercise in Mural (an online tool that can be used for online brainstorming) during the session, focused on developing vision canvases. These exercises provided participants with a structured yet flexible framework to collaboratively define key governance priorities, identify challenges, and explore innovative pathways for long-term transformation. The results of this exercise offer valuable insights into how each

region envisions its governance future, the strategic actions required to achieve it, and the collective commitments necessary to sustain progress beyond the immediate project timeframe.

Contextualisation and Methodological Alignment

This session built on the broader objectives of Work Package 1 (WP1), which focuses on understanding and improving governance processes within and between the demonstrator regions. The decision to use Mural as a dynamic co-creation tool was driven by the need to provide an interactive and visually supported environment that enables multi-actor collaboration remotely. In line with previously developed best practices within the project, this approach offered an accessible way to collect ideas, structure visions, and jointly define priorities—even when in-person meetings were not possible.

The strength of the Mural method lies in its flexibility and user-friendliness: participants were able to contribute simultaneously, build on each other's input, and gain visual insight into shared themes and differences. Moreover, the Mural page remained accessible after the session, allowing demonstrator regions to continue working on their input at their own pace. This enabled stakeholders who could not participate live to still actively contribute to the vision-building process. This asynchronous approach increased inclusivity and led to broader and more thoughtful input. As such, the method is well aligned with WP1's goal of promoting inclusive governance approaches and innovative participation tools.

At the same time, some limitations of the method became evident. Not all stakeholders are equally familiar with digital tools, which may result in unequal levels of participation. Meaningful engagement also requires sufficient preparation time, which was not always feasible given the time constraints of some stakeholders. Additionally, Mural can lack the depth and spontaneous interaction of physical workshops, which can be especially disadvantageous when tackling more complex governance issues.

By combining these insights with the broader learnings from WP1 and other project activities, this exercise contributes to a growing knowledge base on participatory governance. The outcomes provide useful guidance for scaling up successful practices and enhancing systemic impact both within and beyond the demonstrator regions.

Laying the foundation: general vision canvas exercise

Participants engaged in a general brainstorming exercise using the Vision Canvas to kick off the workshop. This session aimed to create a shared understanding of governance challenges and opportunities, setting the stage for more region-specific discussions later. Unfortunately, not all demonstrator sites were represented during the brainstorming session. However, we sent the recording of the entire session and the link to the Mural canvas to those who were not present so they could complete the exercise afterwards.

The exercise revealed a collective vision centred on commitment, fairness in agreements, political impact, and the use of technological innovations to involve all relevant stakeholders. Participants emphasised the need for a collaborative governance approach that goes beyond traditional silos, ensuring long-term sustainability and inclusive decision-making.

A key takeaway from the discussion was the importance of commitment and active participation from all actors to sustain engagement throughout the governance process. Equally critical was the need for fair and equitable agreements that reflect the interests of all involved parties, preventing imbalances or exclusions. The discussion also highlighted the necessity of political impact, ensuring that governance initiatives influence policy and drive systemic change. In addition, participants recognised the potential of technological innovation in making governance more inclusive, enabling broader stakeholder participation through accessible and user-friendly solutions.

Supporting factors such as peer learning, strong networks, and cross-sector collaboration emerged as essential in achieving these governance objectives. Some participants saw value in creating structured spaces for interaction, such as Living Labs, where innovative governance approaches could be tested and refined in real-world settings. At the same time, the discussion revealed significant challenges, particularly in how governance issues are communicated by demonstrator regions. The lack of available time among stakeholders was identified as a major barrier to sustained engagement, along with the difficulty of balancing short-term objectives with long-term strategic goals. Concerns were also raised about ensuring the continuity of governance initiatives beyond the project's timeframe and the persistent challenge of breaking down sectoral silos, especially in regions like Galicia, where stronger intersectoral collaboration is needed.

Overall, this exercise provided valuable insights into both the aspirations and obstacles of multi-actor governance. While there was a strong shared commitment to inclusive and impactful governance, it became clear that structural collaboration, time management, and long-term planning remain significant challenges. These findings set the groundwork for the region-specific discussions that followed, where participants explored how to translate this vision into concrete governance strategies.

To provide a comprehensive overview of the individual governance approaches developed by each demonstrator region, the results of the specific Vision Canvas exercises conducted per region are included as an appendix at the end of this report.

1.7 Key tips and conclusions

a. Do's:

To successfully implement a multi-actor approach to governance, it is essential to adopt key practices that foster collaboration, innovation, and long-term impact. The following do's provide actionable guidelines to strengthen partnerships, ensure sustainability, and drive meaningful transformation.

- 1. Foster inclusive and transparent collaboration:** Actively engage all relevant stakeholders from different sectors and ensure their voices are heard and included in the decision-making process. Maintain transparency in all governance processes by regularly sharing information and outcomes. This approach builds trust and leads to more robust, diverse, and innovative governance models.
- 2. Promote a shared vision and long-term commitment:** Align stakeholders around a common agenda and shared vision for the future. Encourage a sustained focus on long-term goals and solutions, ensuring collaboration is not driven by short-term interests or political cycles.
- 3. Integrate diverse knowledge and build on existing solutions:** Tap into the tacit knowledge of local actors and communities, as their insights and real-world experience are invaluable. Avoid starting from scratch by building on successful existing solutions from other contexts, which saves time and resources.
- 4. Encourage risk-taking and innovation through learning:** Foster an environment where stakeholders feel safe to experiment and take calculated risks. Implement structured processes for regular reflection and learning to continuously assess progress, identify challenges, and adapt strategies.
- 5. Use a systemic approach and scenario planning:** Take a holistic perspective when addressing challenges by looking at the interconnectedness of various factors and actors. Use scenario planning tools to evaluate different futures and strategies, which allows coalitions to prepare for uncertainty and make informed decisions.

6. **Build on existing solutions:** Instead of always starting from scratch, leverage and adapt existing solutions that have proven successful in other regions or contexts. This approach saves time and resources, allowing for faster implementation and greater impact.

By following these "do's," coalitions and governance systems can enhance their effectiveness, foster sustainable solutions, and create an environment of continuous collaboration and innovation.

b. Don't's (Avoiding pitfalls):

While there are many opportunities in a multi-actor approach to governance, ensuring sustainable and effective transformation requires building on lessons learned. The following principles highlight how to strengthen governance practices and avoid common challenges:

1. **Evolve beyond traditional governance structures:** Replace rigid, top-down approaches with more flexible and participatory frameworks that enable broad stakeholder engagement and innovation.
2. **Commit to long-term continuity:** Design governance processes that extend beyond short-term fixes, ensuring momentum is maintained and fragmentation is avoided.
3. **Adapt to local realities:** Ground governance models in local contexts and needs rather than applying uniform, one-size-fits-all solutions.
4. **Make co-creation meaningful:** Ensure collaboration goes beyond symbolic gestures by embedding trust-building, shared ownership, and continuous engagement.
5. **Tackle systemic challenges:** Move beyond isolated initiatives to address structural issues that can unlock lasting transformative change.
6. **Leverage tacit knowledge:** Actively integrate informal expertise, lived experience, and practical know-how to design solutions that are both realistic and sustainable.
7. **Adopt sustainable time horizons:** Build patience and flexibility into governance processes, allowing for iteration, adaptation, and long-term learning.
8. **Develop replicable and scalable models:** Move from reflection to action by creating systematic, evidence-based approaches, such as the D1.3 review, that can be shared and replicated across contexts.

By embedding these principles, governance can remain inclusive, adaptive, and impactful, laying the foundation for meaningful and lasting transformation.

c. Conclusions:

Successful governance and innovation require a **multi-actor approach**, where diverse stakeholders collaborate. Mini-coalitions, in particular, can be powerful drivers of progress, bringing together a wealth of expertise, perspectives, and resources.

To ensure long-term sustainability and resilience, we must **move beyond short-term thinking** often dictated by political cycles and instead foster long-term commitments from all stakeholders. This allows coalitions to withstand political or economic shifts and focus on enduring solutions.

A **systemic perspective** is crucial for transformative change, involving scenario exploration, capacity building, and the integration of tacit knowledge. This enables systems to be more adaptable, sustainable, and resilient.

Furthermore, the importance of **tacit knowledge**, particularly that held by local stakeholders, cannot be overstated. It ensures that solutions are contextually relevant, feasible, and sustainable, and prevents an over-reliance on purely technological or top-down approaches. Innovation must be an ongoing, inclusive

process, involving stakeholders at every level and fostering transparency and collaboration to maintain a dynamic and adaptable system.

Coalitions formed today should be **dynamic**, evolving to address emerging challenges through constant reassessment of goals, strategies, and partnerships, ensuring their continued relevance in evolving social and environmental contexts.

Finally, a **commitment to social resilience and sustainability** is essential for long-term governance success. By focusing on capacity building, resource prioritisation, and allocation, coalitions can achieve results that extend beyond typical governance cycles.

2.0 Best Practice report on TransformAr and Transformational Adaptation Retrospective

2.1 Introduction

This report provides a summary of the key insights and outcomes from the final best practices session of the TransformAr project. The session brought together various consortium partners with the goal of reflecting on the project and the concept of transformational adaptation. The workshop followed a clear, interactive structure to gather comprehensive feedback.

The first phase involved a general look back at the TransformAr project, with participants asked to share what went well and what was difficult from their perspective. The insights were captured on a Mural canvas to ensure all input was recorded. In the second phase, an explanation of the TransformAr Scorecard, a tool developed by the University of Antwerp team to assess the "transformational character" of climate adaptation projects, was provided. This was followed by a practical exercise where participants filled in the scorecard for one of their demonstrator solutions. The third and final phase focused on group reflection. Participants discussed the results from their scorecards and noted down how to improve lower scores in the future or in future projects. They also used the Mural canvas to identify key questions and action points from the exercise.

Overall, the session provided valuable insights into both the successes and challenges of the project. The discussions revealed that while many solutions demonstrated transformative characteristics, there is still significant potential for improvement. The findings will be used to inform future work and help bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and the practical implementation of transformational adaptation.

2.2 Looking back on TransformAr

The demonstrators shared their successes and challenges from the TransformAr project. The insights gathered provide a critical perspective on the practical implementation of climate adaptation solutions. Each section highlights what worked well in each demonstrator location, from strong stakeholder collaboration and public engagement to the successful implementation of new technologies and methodologies. Equally important, we examine the challenges encountered, including difficulties with private sector engagement, evolving regulations, and long-term project sustainability. This comparative analysis provides valuable lessons for future climate adaptation efforts. On page 31 in the appendix, there is an overview of the different solutions that were implemented in the project.

Lappeenranta, Finland

In **Lappeenranta**, the work was defined by strong collaboration. By using a **Choice Experiment**, the team gained a much deeper understanding of citizens' willingness to participate in stormwater management, which will be invaluable for future decisions and planning. They also held multiple workshops for different stakeholders, which provided crucial feedback and results. Ultimately, they successfully implemented all four of their planned solutions on time.

However, the team faced challenges in showing their results and getting local decision-makers involved. They also realised that citizens should have been brought into the process much earlier. Engaging with some stakeholders was difficult, as many didn't respond to their invitations for workshops or interviews.

West Country Region, UK

In the **West Country Region**, the team saw great engagement and interest from stakeholders, and having many different options allowed them to choose the most appropriate solutions as the work progressed. They built lasting relationships with landowners and partners that will be key for future work. New legal requirements also provided a strong motivation for stakeholders to take action.

Despite these successes, managing the program was challenging due to the large number of stakeholders, which made the timetable hard to control. Calculating the mitigation value and inputs, which change over time, was also a difficult task. The team was also working on innovative approaches to meet government standards that were still evolving, and the emerging field of green finance presented a lack of confidence among some stakeholders.

Guadeloupe, France

In **Guadeloupe**, the team had strong engagement from public institutions working in agriculture, water, and the environment. They held several successful workshops with multiple participants, receiving valuable feedback. The need for climate change adaptation in the agricultural sector was strongly recognised. The **Adaptation Fund** was implemented successfully, receiving great feedback from both financial contributors and beneficiaries. The Adaptation Fund is a financial mechanism established in Guadeloupe to finance concrete projects and programs that are particularly vulnerable to the adverse effects of climate change

A key challenge was the lack of engagement from the private sector, specifically banks and insurance companies, with only one bank contributing to the Adaptation Fund. Similarly, the tourism sector showed little interest, with very few project proposals and significant challenges in implementing the **Nudging solution**, which was hampered by unreliable data. The process for the Adaptation Fund was also slow, as a single project required as many contracts as there were funders, causing significant delays.

Oristano, Italy

In **Oristano**, the team had strong local engagement from fishermen, and their collaboration among partners led to the creation of some very valuable tools. They received positive feedback and a lot of interest in replicating the work at both the local and regional levels.

A significant challenge was keeping stakeholders involved throughout the entire process. The long-term management and maintenance of the solutions still need a formalised governance structure. Initial costs were high, and the team is still working on developing cost-efficiency strategies for future replication.

Galicia, Spain

In **Galicia**, the work aligned well with the **Green Deal objectives**, sharing common goals. The team had broad stakeholder involvement, with representatives from administration, academia, industry, and socio-environmental associations. There was also great interest in replicating the outcomes. The work promoted equality and inclusivity by operating in an economic sector with a predominantly female workforce. A clear, understandable message about climate risks helped boost awareness among all stakeholders, leading to a constructive dialogue and a widely-agreed action plan for future projects.

Challenges arose from the terminology, which was sometimes unfamiliar to those in the field and made it difficult to complete some deliverables, like the bankability report. Getting a harmonized operational plan was also challenging. Additionally, the limited timeframe meant they couldn't get more conclusive insights into the effects of climate change on the mussel and clam sectors.

Egaleo, Greece

In **Egaleo**, the team successfully activated local ecosystems, especially within the educational community. Schools were open to experimenting with climate solutions, and students became powerful advocates in their families and neighbourhoods. The team also built strong connections with other EU projects, which helped them increase visibility and integrate their results into broader strategies. The introduction of microclimate stations and the **Climate Hub Initiative (CHI)** successfully captured public and media attention.

Motivating local actors outside the educational sector was a major challenge. Many stakeholders lacked trust in the municipality or simply said they didn't have time. In some cases, the team had to offer concrete incentives or show quick wins to keep them engaged. Furthermore, designing complex tools like the **INSUR insurance model** and the **DSI** required more technical expertise and time than anticipated.

Gjovik, Norway

In **Gjovik**, the team successfully focused more attention on stormwater management, both at the administrative level and among residents. They implemented a citizen engagement application that works well and is now used for a wide range of issues, including roads, water, and pollution. They also held a successful workshop and observed that people are willing to contribute financially to stormwater solutions. The water quality monitoring with sensors is now fully functional, and they have learned a lot about using the data to measure conductivity, pH, and more.

A key challenge was the inability to implement a **Nature-Based Solution (NBS)** from Lappeenranta because they didn't have a suitable project available. They also could have had better stakeholder and citizen participation earlier in the process. It's also still challenging to ensure that both private and public developers in new projects are properly managing stormwater to prevent damage from extreme weather.

The diverse experiences from our demonstration sites underscore a few key takeaways for future climate adaptation work. A recurring success was the ability to foster strong collaboration with key partners and engage public institutions, which was crucial in Lappeenranta, Oristano, and Guadeloupe. Empowering local communities and educational sectors also proved highly effective in places like Egaleo, turning citizens into powerful advocates.

However, a consistent challenge was engaging the private sector, particularly in Guadeloupe and Egaleo. Maintaining stakeholder involvement over the long term and adapting to evolving legal and financial landscapes, as seen in the West Country Region, also presented significant hurdles. The experiences show that while technical solutions can be successfully implemented, the real work lies in the social and governance aspects, building trust, securing long-term commitment, and navigating complex institutional environments. These lessons are vital for developing robust, scalable, and sustainable climate adaptation strategies.

2.3 Transformational adaptation and the Scorecard

A Framework for Transformational Change

Climate change impacts are intensifying, and traditional, incremental strategies are proving to be inadequate for addressing deep-seated vulnerabilities and long-term risks. While **incremental adaptation** involves small, gradual adjustments to existing systems, **transformational adaptation** is about creating fundamental, systemic changes (for more information on this topic, you can refer to the [Policy Brief on transformational adaptation](#)). This approach addresses the root causes of vulnerability and builds long-term resilience by fundamentally altering our practices and systems.

To help bridge the gap between theory and practice, the **TransformAr Scorecard** was developed as an online self-assessment tool. Its purpose is to help stakeholders assess how "transformational" their climate adaptation projects are. It translates five core principles of transformational adaptation into concrete indicators, making it easier to gauge a project's potential for systemic and lasting change.

The TransformAr Scorecard: How It Works

The scorecard is a user-friendly tool that helps you pinpoint the strengths and weaknesses of a project's transformational potential. It provides valuable insights in less than an hour and actively identifies opportunities for improvement.

The tool can be found on the TransformAr website: <https://scorecard.transformar.eu/>

It's important to understand what the scorecard measures. It assesses whether a project incorporates the elements necessary for systemic and lasting change, but it does **not** measure the actual effectiveness of a solution in terms of risk reduction. Its goal is to provide a holistic assessment of a project's potential for transformation.

The scorecard is based on five core principles:

Figure 5: Five scorecard principles

- **Scope:** How broad is the project's influence? Does it affect a large geographic area, an entire sector, or a significant number of stakeholders?

- **Impact Areas:** Does the project change public beliefs and attitudes towards climate action and evolve governance structures?
- **Depth:** Does the project lead to a core system change? This can be a significant shift in a system's trajectory, the restructuring of technologies and processes, or addressing the root causes of vulnerability rather than just the symptoms.
- **Temporality:** Does the solution have a long-term perspective? This includes whether it's persistent, addresses future risks, generates long-term benefits, and is dynamic enough to adjust to changing conditions.
- **Inclusivity:** Does the project consider broader sustainability factors beyond climate adaptation, such as equity, climate mitigation, and alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?

Figure 6: Logic behind the scorecard

When using the scorecard, it's crucial to first define the specific solution and its scope. You'll answer a series of statements on a five-point scale. Users are encouraged to be critical and honest in their responses to truly reveal the project's limitations and opportunities. The results dashboard will provide individual scores for each criterion, but not an overall score, as the tool is designed to highlight specific areas for improvement rather than a single number. Some demonstrator-specific example results can be found in the next section.

Shortcomings and Complementary Tools

While the TransformAR Scorecard is a valuable addition to existing tools, it's essential to acknowledge its limitations. The timing of the assessment can affect the results, as using it *ex ante* (during project design) may lack complete information, while using it *ex post* (after implementation) may be too late to make significant changes. Scores can also be subjective, depending on who fills out the scorecard and how they interpret the indicators. Finally, the tool doesn't provide a quantitative measure of a solution's effectiveness in reducing climate risks.

Despite these limitations, the scorecard fills a unique gap by focusing specifically on the **transformational component** of adaptation, which is often weak or undefined in other tools. Its subjectivity can be mitigated by making several experts use the scorecard independently. Generally, the scorecard provides a useful tool to identify transformational dimensions that could be improved. To get a more comprehensive perspective, the scorecard can also be used alongside other tools for adaptation assessment, such as:

- **Adaptation Policy Credibility (APC):** Assesses policy progress.
- **REGIENCIE Self-Assessment:** Spots risks of maladaptation.
- **Pathways2Resilience (P2R):** Evaluates local authority resilience capacity.
- **Resilience Maturity Model:** Helps cities identify their stage of resilience.
- **UNDRR MCR2030 Resilience roadmap:** Provides a roadmap for urban resilience.

Figure 7: Other adaptation assessment tools

Used together, these tools can provide a more robust and complete picture of a project's impact and potential, strengthening climate adaptation solutions and moving us toward a more resilient future.

2.4 Transformational adaptation and the TransformAr project: insights from the Mural exercises

The TransformAr Scorecard served as a valuable tool for self-assessment, providing a structured way for demonstrators to reflect on their projects' transformative potential. The feedback and results from the scorecard and follow-up discussions reveal key insights and highlight common themes across the different locations.

A key observation from the scorecard exercise was that a project's transformative characteristics are often social and institutional, not just technical. The scorecard was praised for being a useful tool for this kind of qualitative analysis, although some participants raised questions about the fate of the information entered into the open-field text boxes and whether the tool could be more quantitative to allow for comparisons. It was also noted that the scorecard's value lies in its use as a self-assessment tool to guide future decisions, rather than a reporting instrument.

Demonstrator-Specific Insights

Each demonstrator provided unique insights, revealing how the principles of transformational adaptation apply in different contexts. On page 31 in the appendix, there is an overview of the different solutions that were implemented in the project.

Lappeenranta

In Lappeenranta, the work scored well on Temporality, particularly for its long-term vision and future benefits. The combination of nature-based solutions with real-time monitoring was seen as a key success, as it helped shift attitudes and practices. The work also demonstrated strong potential for Scalability, as the solutions are cost-effective, adaptable to different contexts, and rely on technologies and practices that can be replicated in other regions. However, a negative finding was a perceived weakness in Governance, with reflections suggesting that involving stakeholders and decision-makers earlier in the process could have improved outcomes. Similarly, the work could have been more Equitable by better including vulnerable groups.

West Country Region (WCR)

The West Country Region's solutions stood out for their scalability, with a potential for adaptive features to be rolled out at a larger scale through nutrient neutrality. The solutions were also seen as Persistent, as the actions are simple and can be managed by landowners, securing future benefits. The team noted that the scorecard highlighted the need for more data on community impact and benefits to better assess the solutions' Equitable nature. A challenge was the lack of Depth, specifically in restructuring and changing "business as usual" practices.

Guadeloupe

The Adaptation Fund in Guadeloupe was identified as a persistent solution with a long-term vision, aiming for biannual calls for proposals. The solution was highly scalable and created a new, innovative financial mechanism for adaptation, demonstrating a positive impact on governance. However, its scope is currently limited to the agricultural sector, and there is a need to expand engagement to the tourism and private sectors. The solution's depth was also limited, as it aimed to integrate adaptation into current

practices rather than fundamentally shifting the productive activity itself. The team identified a need for more technical assistance at the local level and stronger engagement with private sector partners.

Oristano

In Oristano, the work was recognised for being scalable, and for its equitable approach in addressing vulnerable aspects of the local community. It was also considered dynamic and flexible. The team's efforts successfully changed beliefs and attitudes and improved governance. The solutions scored positively on depth by addressing root causes and restructuring practices but were not considered "path-shifting."

Galicia

Galicia's demonstrator was notable for its long-term vision, dynamism, and Inclusivity. The solutions' beliefs and attitudes were positively impacted, and the scorecard provided an opportunity for the team to reflect on the concept of "path-shifting," concluding that their work aims to improve management rather than completely change the productive activity. The use of a Pentahelix approach and the inclusion of vulnerable groups were key Inclusivity successes. A negative finding was that the solutions were not directly Synergetic, as they didn't directly reduce CO2 emissions. The team also reflected on the need for more detailed planning and better coordination among demonstrator activities in future work.

Egaleo

Egaleo's solutions scored highly on inclusivity and temporality. The team successfully engaged with schools and vulnerable groups, making the solutions socially embedded and designed to continue beyond the work's timeline. This showed that transformational adaptation isn't just about technical innovation, but about changing how people relate to climate risks. The lowest scores were in governance and financing, as it was difficult to engage with national authorities and secure long-term funding. The scorecard highlighted the need for technical tools to be anchored in specific municipal departments to ensure their longevity.

Gjovik

The use of an application to facilitate information exchange was a key success in Gjovik, as it improved understanding of stormwater issues among both residents and the municipality. This was seen as a scalable solution that could be used by other municipalities. The team's feedback identified weaknesses in path-shifting, noting that while some processes were altered, the work did not fundamentally change the system or the day-to-day lives of citizens. They also pointed out the need to involve all stakeholders, including vulnerable groups, and the lack of a direct contribution to climate mitigation.

Overall, the scorecard provided valuable insights into where transformative characteristics already exist and where they can be strengthened. The feedback suggests that while the solutions themselves are innovative, long-term success requires careful attention to governance, inclusivity, and securing financial and institutional support.

Key Questions and Future Actions

The scorecard exercise not only provided a retrospective on the projects but also served as a forward-looking tool, prompting discussions about future challenges and opportunities. The final workshop session focused on capturing key questions and defining concrete action points for the demonstrators moving forward.

A common theme from the discussions was the need to translate the lessons learned into actionable steps for long-term sustainability. The **Oristano** team, for example, questioned how to best use the results from this "ex post" phase to improve their work and strengthen future changes. Similarly, the **West Country Region (WCR)** team identified a critical question about how to fill technical knowledge gaps to maximize the impact of their solutions.

In response to these reflections, several key action points were identified across the demonstrator sites:

- **Securing Long-Term Impact:** The **WCR** noted that a major challenge is capturing the long-term benefits of solutions that have a slow implementation process, especially when involving local authorities. To address this, they emphasized the need for more effective ways to measure and document long-term changes and benefits.
- **Ensuring Continuity:** In **Egaleo**, a primary action point is to clearly map out internal responsibilities within the municipality. This will help identify which departments can take ownership of the solutions (like the DSI, citizen participation, and Climate Innovation Hub) to ensure they continue after the project concludes.
- **Scaling Up:** Both **Egaleo** and **Guadeloupe** highlighted the need for scaling their solutions. The **Egaleo** team plans to open a dialogue with regional authorities to explore how their methodologies can inform regional adaptation planning. Meanwhile, the **Guadeloupe** team confirmed they will continue their work on the **Adaptation Fund** within the H2020 SystR project, with a second round of projects set to launch in 2026. This demonstrates a clear path for the fund's continued evolution and growth.

This exercise highlighted the transition from project-based solutions to long-term strategies. The demonstrators' focus on mapping responsibilities, securing future funding, and planning for broader, systemic change underscores the value of using a tool like the scorecard to inform and guide future climate adaptation efforts.

2.5 Key tips and conclusions

The insights from the demonstrator sites and the scorecard exercise highlight valuable lessons for anyone working on climate adaptation. Here are some key do's and don'ts that can help guide future efforts toward more transformative outcomes.

Do's

- **Do focus on social and institutional change:** The biggest successes came from changes in beliefs, attitudes, and governance structures, not just from new technology. Activating local communities (like in **Egaleo**) and engaging public institutions (like in **Guadeloupe** and **Oristano**) is key.
- **Do involve stakeholders early and continuously:** Involving people from the beginning builds trust and ensures the solution meets their needs. The scorecard exercise showed that early engagement is crucial for securing long-term buy-in from decision-makers and citizens.

- Do **build solutions that are scalable and persistent**: Consider how a solution can be expanded to a larger area or replicated elsewhere. Solutions that can be managed by local actors, like in the WCR, are more likely to have a lasting impact.
- Do **address root causes**, not just symptoms: A transformative solution fundamentally changes the system. Instead of just adding pipes to handle floods, solutions should address the underlying issues of a changing climate and urban development, as demonstrated in Oristano.
- Do **plan for the long term**: Solutions should have a vision that extends beyond the project's end date. This means securing future funding and mapping out who will take ownership of the solution to ensure it continues to function.
- Do **use tools to assess the transformational nature of solutions ex-ante**: Evaluating a project's potential impact early on helps identify weaknesses and creates room for improvement before implementation.

Don'ts

Experience also shows which practices can limit success and should be approached differently:

- **Limited private sector involvement weakens momentum**; engaging businesses and investors early creates stronger foundations for adaptation.
- **Purely technical fixes rarely endure**; without clear institutional ownership and support, tools risk being abandoned, as seen in Egaleo.
- **Overlooking inclusivity and equity undermines resilience**; vulnerable groups must be considered to ensure benefits are distributed fairly.
- **Rigid planning reduces effectiveness**; flexible, adaptive strategies are essential in the face of dynamic climate conditions.
- **Working in isolation restricts impact**; linking local initiatives to regional and national frameworks helps scale solutions and align with broader policies.

Conclusion

The TransformAr project provided invaluable insights into the practical realities of implementing transformational adaptation. The demonstrator sites proved that while technical solutions are important, the true potential for change lies in social and institutional shifts. The TransformAr Scorecard was a powerful tool for self-reflection, helping the teams identify their successes and weaknesses in a structured way.

The lessons learned are clear: building climate resilience is a multi-faceted process that requires strong partnerships, early and continuous stakeholder engagement, and a long-term vision that moves beyond short-term fixes. By focusing on governance, inclusivity, and scalability, future climate adaptation initiatives can move beyond incremental adjustments and truly create the fundamental, systemic changes needed for a more resilient future.

3.0 References

3.1 Fifth Best Practice Report: A Multi-Actor Approach on governance

O. Bernardez, J. Domingues, N. Rodriguez-Aubo, W. Filipowska, C. Cotelo (2022) Interactive Innovation Broker: a consensual framework for multi-actor approach practical implementation, iceri2022 proceedings, pp. 5298-5302.

FEUGA (2022) Stakeholders' Engagement Guidelines. TransformAr Deliverable 1.1, H2020 grant no. 101036683

3.2 Sixth Best Practice Report: Transformational Adaptation Retrospective

ACTIERRA; Durand S., Gaudimont K., Porko-Beugnet S., Soto A (2025) Sectoral policy recommendations. TransformAr Deliverable 7.1, H2020 grant no. 101036683

Climate-ADAPT – Adaptation Policy Credibility (APC) [https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/tools/008_adaptation-policy-credibility-apc]

Cools et al. (2024). Understanding Transformational Adaptation: A Shared Vision Across EU Horizon Projects. Projects' policy brief under the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change's Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt).

Fabri C., Cools J., (2025) D6.4 Guidance Document on Transformational Adaptation [https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/08/D6.4_summary-sheet_transformational_adaptation.pdf]

ICVA Network – Adaptation Good Practice Checklist and Toolkit [<https://www.icvanetwork.org/resource/adaptation-good-practice-checklist-toolkit-checklist/>]

LCP Initiative – Climate Change Scoring Tool [<https://www.lcp-initiative.eu/climate-change-scoring-tool/>]

Pathways2Resilience – The P2R Self-Assessment Questionnaire [<https://www.pathways2resilience.eu/The-P2RSelf-Assessment-Questionnaire>]

Regilience Project – Self-Assessment Tool for Maladaptation [<https://regilience.eu/self-assessment-tool-for-maladaptation/>]

SMR Project – Maturity Model Guide [<https://smr-project.eu/tools/maturity-model-guide/>]

UNDRR – Resilience Roadmap Stage Assessment [<https://mcr2030.undrr.org/resilience-roadmap/stage-assessment>]

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Figure 7: Other adaptation assessment tools

5.0 Appendix

Overview of the different solutions implemented within the TransformAR project

Solution	Demonstrator/ Location	Type	Short explanation
1 Crowdsourcing Citizen application	Gjøvik, Norway	Awareness-raising and behavioural change	A citizen app for real-time flood detecting and reporting. This app allows residents to submit observations, including photos and locations, which are shared directly with municipal employees.
2 Choice Experiment in Lappeenranta and Gjøvik	Lappeenranta, Finland Gjøvik, Norway	Insurance schemes and financial solutions	A data-driven tool to uncover citizen preferences for green and grey stormwater solutions - empowering cities to drive private investment and climate adaptation through smarter, targeted flood risk policies.
3 Stormwater Monitoring / Modular system	Lappeenranta, Finland Gjøvik, Norway	Digital and technological solutions	Real-time monitoring of the stormwater system: flow rates and water quality to prevent pollution and manage runoff. The user interface is visual and browser-based, enabling access from a smartphone or laptop.
4 Nature-Based Solutions in Lappeenranta	Lappeenranta, Finland	Nature-based solutions	New integrative biofiltration area in the city centre as part of new urban adaptation standards, to reduce the amount of water led to stormwater sewer systems, to filter harmful substances, and to filter stormwater into groundwater.
5 Nature-Based Solutions in the West Country	West Country Region, UK	Nature-based solutions	Nature-based solutions are bespoke, scalable interventions designed to simulate natural processes for holistic environmental improvement. WRT implemented several nature-based solutions in the West Country Region, such as ponds, scrapes, swales, leaky dams, riparian woodland, and buffer strips
6 Payment for ecosystem services	West Country Region, UK	Insurance schemes and financial solutions	Lack of funding is a common issue when aiming to implement adaptation solutions, such as NbS. WRT studied the possibility of private-sector investment

			schemes to support Nature-based solutions through interviews and held workshops to identify models for green finance schemes. The scheme ,Community Interest Company' appeared to have the largest number of benefits.
7	Local adaptation fund	Guadeloupe, France	Insurance schemes and financial solutions The Local Adaptation Fund (AF) is a blended finance tool boosting local climate adaptation in the agriculture and tourism sectors in Guadeloupe. It supports vulnerable groups and offers a replicable model for other climate change-exposed territories.
8	Nudging solution	Guadeloupe, France	Awareness-raising and behavioural change Smart shower sensors and visual nudges motivate hotel guests in Guadeloupe to take shorter showers, saving water and reducing energy use – good for the environment and awareness.
9	Mussel-raft monitoring	Galicia, Spain	Digital and technological solutions CETMAR leads the digitalisation of mussel rafts to enable real-time environmental and production monitoring, tailored to stakeholders' needs. It gathers extensive data to optimise management in the face of climate challenges.
10	Intertidal monitoring	Galicia, Spain	Digital and technological solutions The development of a simple, low-cost methodology for obtaining substrate parameters from sandbanks. This methodology, proposed in cooperation with stakeholders, will allow for the acquisition of long data series, improving knowledge for decision-making.
11	Resilience Index	Galicia, Spain	Governance Schemes The Resilience Index (RI) is a mathematical model that assesses the adaptive capacity of value chain operations to climate change. Its insights guide strategic decision-making and foster scalable solutions for risk management and sustainability.
12	Insurance schemes	All	Insurance schemes and financial solutions Climate change increases the risk of being affected by natural disasters. As a result, dealing with the consequences requires major financial efforts to compensate for losses, and in this context, insurance has attracted much attention lately as a tool in climate risk management. In addition to financial compensation for losses after an

			extreme weather event, insurance can provide incentives to reduce risk, and potential investors often ask for insurance to save their investment.
13	Smart Climate Stations	Egaleo, Greece	Digital and technological solutions MOE focused on the installation of 21 Smart Climate Stations (SCS) around key areas of the city. The purpose of the SCSs is to gather real-time data regarding the micro-climate of the city, supporting the public administration office to ready the citizens in case of climate emergencies. After careful consideration and design, the key areas have been identifying and the SCSs began their operation registering Temperature, Relative Humidity, Atmospheric Pressure, CO2 (ppm), PM 2.5 /10 (ppm), Wind speed and Rainfall.
14	Citizen application	Egaleo, Greece	Awareness-raising and behavioural change A mobile app for gathering and distributed information; (1) it will be used to crowdsource data about climate awareness of citizens of MOE via questionnaire, (2) to disseminate TransformAR's MOE solution to the public and (3) to provide notifications for climate related events
15	Climate Innovation Hub	Egaleo, Greece	Governance schemes/ Awareness-raising and behavioural change A municipal hub combining climate data, permanent exhibitions, and citizen-driven events to enhance awareness, foster innovation, and co-design local adaptation strategies.
16	Students awareness raising	Egaleo, Greece	Awareness-raising and behavioural change A climate education module, empowering 13–15-year-old students to understand climate challenges, co-design adaptation solutions, and build civic capacity.
17	Demand analysis for social services and infrastructure	Egaleo, Greece	Governance schemes A resilience assessment – based on quantifiable metrics – of the social services considering future scenarios
18	Smart Grid and Gates	Oristano, Italy	Nature-based solutions Intelligent and remote-controlled sluice gate that opens automatically based on real-time data, enabling adaptive water flow regulation. Designed to protect ecosystems and support local fisheries, it enhances both environmental and economic resilience
19	Coastal contracts	Oristano, Italy	Governance schemes A voluntary, nature-based governance model uniting public and private

			stakeholders to manage wetlands sustainably and boost climate resilience, based on a structured Action Plan co-designed with local actors.
20	Citizen application	Lappeenranta, Finland	Awareness-raising and behavioural change An application called CitySen. App to involve citizens in flood monitoring and awareness.

Table 1: Overview of the solutions implemented within TransformAr: Severijns, R. et al (2025). Catalogue of Solutions. TransformAr Deliverable 6.3, H2020 grant no. 101036683

BP5: A multi-actor approach to governance

The following appendix presents the detailed governance approaches developed by each demonstrator region during the Vision Canvas exercises, highlighting their unique strategies, challenges, and solutions tailored to their specific contexts."

Summary Lappeenranta:

Vision and Key Points

Lappeenranta focuses on sustainable urban development with an emphasis on stakeholder engagement, public awareness, financial constraints, lack of space for nature-based solutions (NBS), and human resources capacity.

Key Steps

- Management and maintenance plan for nature-based solutions.
- Marketing of the CitySen app to enhance public engagement.
- Collaboration with schools, NGOs, and associations to promote awareness and participation.
- Development of replicable solutions for broader implementation.
- Securing future projects and funding for further development.

Supporting Factors

- Technical solutions such as sensors and apps improve monitoring and implementation.
- A lean organization facilitates efficient communication and decision-making.
- Flexibility and scalability allow adaptation to different environments.
- Real-time access to information enables quick and effective decision-making.
- Funding from European projects supports execution.

Challenges

- Costs and funding of measures remain a challenge.
- Gaining stakeholder attention and engagement is difficult.
- Fragmented environmental data complicates policy-making.
- Lack of time hinders in-depth knowledge development on these topics.

Conclusion

The city focuses on collaboration, technological innovation, and flexibility to implement sustainable solutions, despite challenges related to funding and stakeholder engagement.

Summary of the Vision Canvas – West Country Region

Vision and Key Points

The West Country Region focuses on scaling up climate adaptation solutions (CCA), attracting private investment, and integrating CCA into agricultural and environmental policy.

Key Themes

Scaling up solutions across a wider region.

Combining private finance and government funding for climate adaptation.

Integrating climate adaptation strategies into agricultural and environmental policy.

Supporting Factors

Local collaboration through existing networks and groups.

Funding from EU projects and government schemes for specific actions.

Existing funding from water companies and ESG private sector investments.

Challenges

Identifying which initiatives will remain effective in the region over the long term.

Embedding climate adaptation strategies into agricultural and land-use policy.

Ensuring sufficient private funding for the full range of adaptation measures.

Conclusion:

The region aims to leverage both public and private resources to implement large-scale climate adaptation, with a strong focus on policy integration and the long-term sustainability of initiatives.

Summary of the Vision Canvas – Guadeloupe

Vision and Key Points

Guadeloupe focuses on political involvement, private sector engagement, and reducing bureaucratic barriers to support climate adaptation.

Supporting Factors

ADEME's role as a state-funded agency provides structural support.

Positive feedback on funding initiatives encourages further investments.

Involvement of various local institutions strengthens collaboration.

Challenges

Engaging the tourism sector in climate adaptation, particularly the private sector.

Difficulty in securing political support for the FLAG initiative.

Bureaucratic burden of grant applications, making it challenging for beneficiaries.

Conclusion

Guadeloupe aims to foster collaboration between public and private sectors but faces challenges such as bureaucratic complexity and securing political support for climate initiatives.

Summary of the Vision Canvas – Oristano

Vision and Key Points

Oristano focuses on long-term strategies for wetland restoration, engagement with stakeholders, and the adaptation of economic activities (such as fishing and agriculture) to climate change. The area also emphasizes the conservation of the lagoon/wetland as a valuable local resource.

Key Steps Towards the Vision

Management and maintenance plan for the wetland (SG).

Dissemination of the LWO (Local Wetland Observations) and related findings.

Update the coastal action plan (AP) with results from the pathways.

Replicability of the SG system and monitoring system for broader application.

Seek additional funding to complete the wetland restoration.

Supporting Factors

Coastal contract for sustainable management.

Regional adaptation strategy supporting the overall effort.

New projects in the same area help build consensus, knowledge, and secure funding for further development.

Challenges

Long-term viability of the solution and its sustainability.

Integrating solutions into agricultural practices and ensuring the farming community adopts climate adaptation strategies.

Embedding climate adaptation pathways into agriculture, fisheries, and environmental protection policies.

Maintaining smart gates and monitoring systems, which require stable funding.

Extending adaptation efforts, such as bridging harbors and other infrastructure improvements.

Challenges with SG authorization processes, involving multiple entities, price increases, technical difficulties, and differing implementation teams.

Conveying the added value of solutions to stakeholders, particularly in the fishing sector.

Communicating the need for concrete, unified coastal management to stakeholders.

Lack of communication of environmental data with stakeholders, despite existing monitoring systems.

Conclusion

Oriстано is focused on wetland restoration, engaging stakeholders, and adapting local economic activities to climate change. Despite strong foundational support and clear steps forward, the region faces challenges in long-term solution viability, policy integration, stakeholder communication, and securing ongoing funding.

Summary of the Vision Canvas – Galicia

Vision and Key Points

Galicia focuses on long-term engagement, securing funding, improving access to information, evaluating adaptation potential, and establishing a robust policy framework. The region also aims to break siloes and increase involvement across sectors for a more integrated approach to climate adaptation.

Key Themes

Long-term engagement with stakeholders to ensure continuous participation and adaptation.

Funding to support ongoing projects, with grants available until 2026.

Availability and access to information for timely and effective decision-making.

Adaptation potential for key sectors such as mussel and clam aquaculture.

Policy framework to integrate climate adaptation strategies effectively.

Breaking siloes by increasing cross-sector involvement and collaboration.

Supporting Factors

Direct communication channels with the sector to enable real adaptation to its needs.

5 helix stakeholder involvement ensures diverse participation from all relevant groups.

Funds available until 2026 to secure long-term project sustainability.

Real-time information access for better decision-making.

Flexibility and replicability of strategies allow for adaptation and expansion.

Extensive media coverage of results to raise awareness and encourage wider participation.

Challenges

Regulatory framework gaps, particularly between data analysis and policy updates, which can slow down necessary changes.

Data dependency, as long-term monitoring is crucial for understanding climate change impacts on mussel and clam aquaculture.

Climate change uncertainty and variability require regular updates to the resilience index, but limited monitoring (only two years of mussel raft monitoring) hampers reliable extrapolation of results.

Resource intensity: The resilience index (RI) requires significant time and digital technological solutions, which are challenging in a marine environment.

Balancing stakeholder involvement: Ensuring sufficient engagement from stakeholders without overloading them with workshops, surveys, and questionnaires.

Conclusion

Galicia aims to create a long-term, adaptable climate adaptation framework through multi-stakeholder involvement, securing funding, and leveraging real-time data. However, the region faces challenges in regulatory gaps, data limitations, resource intensity, and ensuring balanced stakeholder engagement.

Summary of the Vision Canvas – Egaleo

Vision and Key Points

Egaleo focuses on the development of smart climate stations, the creation of a citizen app, raising citizen (students) awareness, establishing a climate innovation hub, and conducting a demand analysis for social services/infrastructures. The aim is to integrate these elements to foster a more sustainable and informed community, with strong stakeholder collaboration.

Key Themes

Smart Climate Stations to monitor environmental data and inform climate actions.

Citizen App to engage the public in climate-related activities and information sharing.

Citizen (students) Awareness to raise climate awareness among local residents, especially students.

Climate Innovation Hub to promote innovative solutions and serve as a focal point for climate initiatives.

Demand Analysis for Social Services/Infrastructure to understand the needs of the community and adapt services accordingly.

Supporting Factors

Collaboration between public, private, and civil society organizations within the living labs.

Funds from European projects to support the initiatives.

Sustainability of actions, as they are connected to other European and national environmental projects.

Challenges

Lack of an official Civil Protection Department in the municipality of Egaleo.

Limited stakeholder engagement, as stakeholders often lack free time to participate in the living labs; motivation is needed to encourage their involvement.

Inefficient collaboration between municipal departments, hindering seamless implementation of actions.

Conclusion

Egaleo is focused on building smart, citizen-engaged climate solutions, with a strong emphasis on collaboration across sectors and sustainability through European funding. However, the municipality faces challenges related to stakeholder engagement, lack of civil protection structures, and inter-departmental collaboration.

Summary of the Vision Canvas – Gjøvik

Vision and Key Points

Gjøvik focuses on increasing public awareness, improving event prediction and warning systems, implementing financial and legal measures, separating stormwater from wastewater, and promoting nature-based solutions such as open waterways. These actions are aimed at enhancing climate resilience and improving water management in the region.

Key Themes

Increase Public Awareness to engage the community in climate and water management issues.

Event Prediction and Warning to improve preparedness for climate-related events such as storms and floods.

Financial and Legal Measures to provide the necessary funding and legal framework to support climate adaptation actions.

Separation of Stormwater from Wastewater to enhance infrastructure and reduce environmental impact.

Nature-based Solutions and Open Waterways to integrate natural systems in water management and promote sustainable urban planning.

Supporting Factors

Technical solutions such as sensors and apps that assist in monitoring and decision-making.

Legislation and strategy provide the necessary framework for implementing climate adaptation measures.

Challenges

Financing and cost of measures remain a key challenge, as the implementation of these solutions requires significant investment.

Getting stakeholders' attention and participation is difficult, as their involvement is essential for the success of these initiatives.

Conclusion

Gjøvik is focusing on a combination of public awareness, technological solutions, and nature-based strategies to address climate challenges, particularly in water management. Despite strong support through legislation and strategy, the region faces challenges in securing funding and ensuring stakeholder engagement.

BP6: Looking back on TransformAr and transformational adaptation

This section contains a summary of the data and insights gathered on the **Mural canvas** during the best practice session. The information is structured by demonstrator area, and the collaborative canvas remained accessible to all participants for continued contributions.

Looking back on TransformAr:

1. Lappeenranta

What went well?

- Collaboration with our project partners, especially with technical partner LUT and replicator MOG.
- Due to Choice experiment, we now have a better understanding of citizen's willingness to participate in stormwater management and can utilize that information in the future decisions and planning.
- Organized multiple workshops for different stakeholders. Received valuable feedback and results.
- We successfully implemented all 4 solutions in time

What was challenging?

- Showcasing the results.
- Involving local decision makers.
- We could have involved citizens earlier in the project phase.
- Engaging stakeholders; e.g. workshop invitations and bankability interviews (most stakeholders didn't answer anything and didn't participate)

2. West Country Region (WCR)

What went well?

- Good engagement & Interest from stakeholders
- Lots of options meant we could choose the most appropriate as the project developed

What was challenging?

- Developed ongoing relationships with landowners and partners for future work
- New legal requirements helped motivate the stakeholders to take action
- Multiple stakeholders made programme challenging - we didn't have control of the timetable
- Being able to calculate the inputs and mitigation value which vary over time
- Innovative approach trying to meet standards that were still evolving from government
- Lack of confidence in green finance as this is still emerging

3. Guadeloupe

What went well?

- Good engagement from public institutions working on agriculture/water/environment
- We organized several workshops with multiple participants and received valuable feedback
- Strong recognition of the need for climate change adaptation in the agriculture sector
- Successful implementation of the AF with very good feedback from both financial contributors and beneficiaries

What was challenging?

- Lack of engagement from the private sector (banks, insurances etc.) Only one bank contributed to the AF
- Lack of engagement from the tourism sector: very few project proposals from the tourism sector for the AF (and none selected) + the implementation of the NUDG solution was really challenging
- Lack of awareness of climate change adaptation, especially from the private sector and the tourism sector
- Challenges in implementing NUDG solutions = data not very reliable
- The functioning of the AF (where one project required as many contracts as there were funders) caused significant delays in project implementation, as processes such as deliberations

by local authorities, issuance of contracts to beneficiaries from multiple funders, and fund disbursements were particularly time-consuming.

4. Oristano

What went well?

- **Strong local engagement of fishermen**
- **Good collaboration among partners** leading to the development of valuable tools
- Positive feedback and interest in replicability at local and regional level

What was challenging?

- Keep stakeholders involved throughout the whole project
- Long-term management and maintenance still need a formalized governance structure
- Initial costs were high. Cost-efficiency strategies for replication are still being developed.

5. Galicia

What went well?

- While aligning the demos with the Green Deal objectives presents certain challenges, it becomes clear that they share common aims in the end
- Stakeholder involvement (representation of administration, academy, industry, socio-environmental associations...)
- Transfer of the outcomes and interest in replication
- Our demonstrator operated in an economic sector with a predominantly female workforce, promoting equality and inclusivity (INTERM).
- A dissemination effort focused on a clear and understandable message for all stakeholders about climate risks and their impact on the sector boosted awareness.
- Interesting dialogue among STH that led the construction of a broadly agreed-upon action plan (many of them approved to be implemented with future projects and funding)

What was challenging?

- The terminology and certain aspects of the project are somewhat removed from the usual working methods in the field of science, which has made it difficult to complete some deliverables (bankability as an example)
- To get the operational plan of the project for better harmonize activities at the demo level
- Some conclusions were obtained but the timeframe was limited to reach more conclusive insights into the effects of climate change on mussel and clam sectors

6. Egaleo

What went well?

- We successfully activated local ecosystems in Egaleo, especially the educational community. Schools were open to experimenting with climate solutions and students became powerful awareness multipliers in their families and neighborhoods.
- We also established strong synergies between TransformAR and other EU projects (e.g. RockTheBlock, MED-IREN), which helped us scale visibility and integrate outcomes into wider strategies.
- The microclimate stations and the Hub (CHI) increased visibility and triggered public interest and media attention.

What was challenging?

- It was challenging to motivate local actors, especially outside the educational sector. Many stakeholders lacked trust in the municipality or claimed they didn't have time to participate.
- In some cases, we needed to provide very concrete incentives or show quick wins to keep them engaged.
- Designing complex tools like the insurance model (INSUR) or DSI required more technical capacity and time than expected.

7. Gjovik

What went well?

- We achieved better focus on stormwater management, both at the administrative level and among residents.
- We implemented an application for citizen engagement, which works well and is now used for more than just stormwater-related issues. It also used for roads, water, sewage, agriculture, and pollution. Messages can also be posted for the residents.
- We conducted a successful workshop.
- We observe a certain willingness among the population to contribute financially to stormwater measures.
- We have functioning water quality monitoring for Storm water. And we have learned a lot about the use of sensors. We have measured conductivity, salinity, TDS, pH, turbidity, and volume. We are logging the data and exploring how to use it going forward.

What was challenging?

- We were not able to implement a Nature-Based Solution (NBS) for replication from Lappeenranta. We did not have any suitable projects available for implementation; the one we had planned to use was postponed.
- Ideally, there could have been higher stakeholder participation.
- We could have involved citizens earlier in the project phase.
- It can be challenging in new projects to ensure that stormwater is managed in a better way to reduce pollution and damage during extreme weather events. This applies to both private and public developers.

Feedback from filling in the scorecard:

- Not clear we could not access the results → already mentioned in the intro on the page
- What happens with the input from the open fields? Is this saved somewhere or used in the results on the dashboard?

Results from the Mural canvas

1. Lappeenranta

What stands out?

- Long term vision and future benefits of the NBS combined with real-time monitoring and presenting this information to public. This shapes both attitude and local/regional practices.

What insights do the scorecards provide on the impact of the solutions

- Impacts on beliefs and attitudes

Where do we see already transformative characteristics?

- Long term vision, future benefits.

Zoom in on the key principles:

- Scope
 - Positive
 - Scalable
 - Negative
 - /
- Impact areas
 - Positive
 - Beliefs and attitudes
 - Negative
 - Governance
- Depth
 - Positive
 - Addressing root causes
 - Negative
 - /
- Temporality
 - Positive
 - Persistent, long term vision, future benefits, dynamic
 - Negative
 - /
- Inclusivity
 - Positive
 - SDG-aligned

- Negative
 - Equitable

How could this be improved in the future:

- Involving stakeholders and decision makers at earlier stage.
- Involving vulnerable groups.

2. West Country Region (WCR)

What stands out?

- Scalable
- Persistent
- Future benefits

What insights do the scorecards provide on the impact of the solutions

- The fact that it is relicable and rolled out at a bigger scale

Where do we see already transformative characteristics?

- Potential for adaptive feature to be rolled out through nutrient neutrality

Zoom in on the key principles:

- Scope
 - Positive
 - Scalable
 - Negative
 - Address related causes of pollution such as septic tanks
- Impact areas
 - Positive
 - Input as partner at Local Authority level on strategy for the issue
 - Negative
 - Input as partner at Local Authority level on strategy for the issue
- Depth
 - Positive
 -
 - Negative
 - Restructuring - changing business as usual
- Temporality
 - Positive
 - Persistent - simple replicable actions that can be managed by landowners
 - Negative
 - Hard to monitor from satellite mapping - develop accessible ways to evidence the benefits

- Inclusivity
 - Positive
 - Many co-benefits especially biodiversity
 - Negative
 - Equitable- not enough data/info gathered on community impact

How could this be improved in the future:

- Continue to develop and support community leaders in best practice
- More data on community impact/Benefits

3. Guadeloupe

What stands out?

- Persistent solution with long-term vision
- Scalable and possibilities of improvements in the future

What insights do the scorecards provide on the impact of the solutions

- /

Where do we see already transformative characteristics?

- /

Zoom in on the key principles:

- Scope
 - Positive
 - Multistakeholder coordination, engagement of diverse institutions + 1 private
 - Highly scalable and replicable
 - Negative
 - Limited to the agriculture sector for now (no projects from the tourism sector selected, and only a few received)
- Impact areas
 - Positive
 - The project resulted in the creation of a novel financial mechanism for adaptation, fostering a new model of cooperation between institutions and between the public and private sector.
 - A financial and technical committee has been established to oversee the selection of projects
 - Negative
 - The impact of the solution in terms of new regulations, policies can be strengthened

- Depth
 - Positive
 - The solution creates a new, innovative financial mechanism which doesn't exist in France
 - The projects funded through the AF are innovative, incorporating digital and technological solutions to enhance the agricultural sector's resilience to climate change.
 - Negative
 - Path-shifting: the solution doesn't intend to change the productive activity but rather integrate adaptation considerations into current practices
- Temporality
 - Positive
 - Solution with long-term vision : ambition is to launch biannual calls for projects
 - The Adaptation Fund (AF) is a dynamic mechanism with potential for evolution including possible changes in governance and expansion into other sectors.
 - Negative
 - NUDG : no long-term vision
- Inclusivity
 - Positive
 - The AF is now focusing on farmers which are highly affected by climate change
 - Negative
 - The focus is now only on agriculture. Could be expanded to other vulnerable areas/populations in the future

How could this be improved in the future:

- Inclusion of local stakeholders in the whole project, to make them feel like they are "part of something big"
- More discussions with the private sector, showing them the value of investing in climate adaptation strategies
- Anticipate: establish agreements with public institutions to secure dedicated budget allocations for the AF
- Drafting of a framework agreement on adaptation in Guadeloupe, which will outline the territory's adaptation pathways as well as the operating principles of the AF
- Raising awareness within the tourism sector about the impacts of climate change + expanding engagement to other sectors
- Need for technical assistance at the local level (e.g. it was not the case for NUDG)

4. Oristano

What stands out?

- Scalable
- Addressing vulnerable aspects
- Dynamic and flexible approach

What insights do the scorecards provide on the impact of the solutions

- /

Where do we see already transformative characteristics?

- /

Zoom in on the key principles:

- Scope
 - Positive
 - Scalable
 - Negative
 - Systemwide (benefits for the wetland ecosystem and fishing sectors, but no benefits so far for other regions)
- Impact areas
 - Positive
 - Beliefs and attitude
 - Governance
 - Negative
 - /
- Depth
 - Positive
 - Restructurings
 - Addressing root causes
 - Negative
 - Path shifting
- Temporality
 - Positive
 - Future benefits
 - Dynamics
 - Negative
 - /
- Inclusivity
 - Positive
 - Equitable
 - Synergetic
 - SDG-Aligned
 - Negative
 - /

How could this be improved in the future:

- /

5. Galicia

What stands out?

- LongTerm Vision, Dynamic, and inclusivity (INTERM, MRM)
- Impact areas and Depth (RI)

What insights do the scorecards provide on the impact of the solutions

- Reflection on the need of Path-shifting or not

Where do we see already transformative characteristics?

- Beliefs and attitudes, Long term vision

Zoom in on the key principles:

- Scope
 - Positive
 - Scalable (MRM, INTERM, RI)
 - Transferable (MRM)
 - Multi-scale (RI)
 - Negative
 - Systemwide (INTERM, RI)
- Impact areas
 - Positive
 - Beliefs and attitudes (MRM, INTERM, RI)
 - Governance (MRM, RI)
 - Negative
 - Governance (INTERM)
- Depth
 - Positive
 - Addressing root causes, reporting by stakeholders (MRM, INTERM, RI)
 - Restructuring (MRM, RI)
 - Negative
 - Path-shifting (MRM, RI) It is not oriented to change the productive activity but to improve the management, however, deeper reflection can be made about this concept
- Temporality
 - Positive
 - Future benefits/dynamic (MRM, INTERM, RI)
 - Long term vision (RI)
 - Dynamic (RI)

- Negative
 - Not permanent / Depends on funding and STH will.
 - Persistent (RI), because some of the questions in this section are focused on an environmental intervention, not so suitable for a decision-making tool.
- Inclusivity
 - Positive
 - Pentahelix approach Vulnerable groups inclusion
 - Equitable
 - SDG-aligned
 - Negative
 - Synergetic (RI), as the solution has no direct effect on reducing CO2 emissions and/or pollution

How could this be improved in the future:

- More detailed planning of activities for the whole project, including demos
- Coordination meetings focused on demos
- To include an extra final phase to guide more in depth the formulation of new policies based on the RI insights.
- Include these analysis before and after the implementation period

6. Egaleo

What stands out?

Positive results:

- The solutions in Egaleo scored high in inclusivity and public engagement. We worked closely with schools and vulnerable groups, which made the solutions more socially embedded.
- Temporality also stood out as a strength: several of our actions (like the awareness-raising modules, CHI, and microclimate stations) are designed to continue beyond the project timeline.
- The solutions are replicable and expandable, and some are already being used in other initiatives at local level.

Negative results / challenges:

- The lowest scores were related to multi-level governance and policy integration. Although we collaborated with the municipal departments, we did not manage to engage national or regional authorities in a structured way.
- Financing also remains uncertain for long-term continuity, especially for complex tools like the insurance mechanism (INSUR).

What insights do the scorecards provide on the impact of the solutions

- The scorecard helped us reflect on which solutions have the strongest social impact — especially those involving direct citizen participation, like the awareness-raising modules and the Climate Innovation Hub.

- It confirmed that long-term impact is more likely when the solution is embedded in existing municipal services or networks.
- It also highlighted that transformational adaptation is not only about technical innovation, but about changing how people relate to climate risks — and this was a key success in our educational work.
- On the other hand, it showed us that technical tools alone (like the insurance mechanism or risk models) need stronger institutional integration to truly make a difference.

Where do we see already transformative characteristics?

- We see transformative characteristics especially in the way citizens and schools actively engaged in the design and implementation of solutions.
- The Climate Innovation Hub (CHI) is a good example of a new form of collaboration — it brought together social services, citizens, and entrepreneurs in a shared space for climate and community action.
- The educational programmes (AWAR) shifted the role of students from passive learners to active climate ambassadors, which created ripple effects in the wider community.
- We also notice a shift in mindset among municipal staff, who are now more open to participatory planning and cross-department collaboration.

How could this be improved in the future:

- In future projects, we would invest more time and effort in early engagement with regional and national authorities, to align our local work with higher-level policy and funding frameworks.
- We also learned that technical solutions need clear ownership from the beginning — for example, the insurance and data tools need to be anchored in specific departments or external partners to be sustained.
- Another area for improvement is to create a stronger link between community participation and decision-making, so that citizen input is visibly reflected in municipal strategies.
- Finally, we would allocate more resources to capacity building, especially for complex tools, so that local actors feel more confident using and maintaining them.

7. Gjovik

What stands out?

- The use of an app to facilitate information exchange between residents and the municipality proved successful.

What insights do the scorecards provide on the impact of the solutions

- better understanding of stormwater issues

Where do we see already transformative characteristics?

- This improved understanding of stormwater challenges can be transferred to new projects and serve as a valuable reference for other municipalities.

Zoom in on the key principles:

- Scope
 - Positive
 - We see that this or at least parts of it can be used by other municipalities and in private development.
 - Negative
 - the adaptation project's scope could be increased by collaborating with the regional authorities (e.g., proposing the solutions to be implemented outside of Gjøvik) or by expanding the solutions through different funding sources.
- Impact areas
 - Positive
 - This is important in order to be able to find new solutions, we see that citizens are willing to pay for simple solutions. Developers must be governed by regulations nationally or locally
 - Negative
 - 1. Path-shifting: although both solutions contribute to responding more rapidly to heavy rainfall events, the adaptation project does not fundamentally change the system. Some processes within the local government are altered, but the adaptation project does not affect the municipality's general focus or the day-to-day lives of its citizens.
- Depth
 - Positive
 - Important to determine where the responsibility lies, either with private, local authorities or state authorities
 - Negative
 - as co-production is a crucial part of transformational adaptation, future changes to either of the solutions should ideally be consulted with citizens. What are the needs of citizens with regards to the Citizen App, for example? Is the process of reporting flooding events sufficiently user-friendly? Are there additional features which they would like? How can the municipality, according to them, best respond to floods and avoid damage?
- Temporality
 - Positive
 - Long-term plans and a framework that is easy to understand must be created.
 - Negative
 - special consideration of vulnerable citizens. Even to date, after implementing both solutions, vulnerable citizens such as elderly can still be considered by questioning them about their satisfaction with the Citizen App. What could be

improved or which alternatives could be provided to ensure that they benefit from the solutions at least as much as non-vulnerable citizens?

- Inclusivity
 - Positive
 - It is important to involve everyone who is affected. Today, plans are decided without any significant participation from residents or private developers.
 - Negative
 - the adaptation solutions do not contribute to climate mitigation. This could be improved by, for example, integrating energy-saving advice for citizens in the Citizen App, raising awareness about energy consumption and carbon-based transport.

How could this be improved in the future:

- Have a clearer framework for what and where the project is going. Clarify roles in the project early and closely follow up on project delivery times. Involve partners, stakeholders and residents early in the project.

Groep reflections

1. Lappeenranta

Questions:

- /

Action points:

- /

2. West Country Region (WCR)

Questions:

- What technical knowledge gaps can we fill to make projects more impactful

Action points:

- Some of these actions/features are a slow process to get going, so need to be able to capture long term/change and benefits

3. Guadeloupe

Questions:

- /

Action points:

- We will continue working on the AF within the H2020 SystR project, focusing on systemic adaptation. A 2nd round of projects will be launched in 2026

4. Oristano

Questions:

- How could we really use the results in this ex post phase?
- How can we improve the project in the future to make the changes more strong?

Action points:

- /

5. Galicia

Questions:

- /

Action points:

- /

6. Egaleo

Questions:

- /

Action points:

- One action point is to map the internal responsibilities in the municipality more clearly, to identify where each solution could continue after the project.
- Another is to open dialogue with regional authorities to explore how TransformAr methodologies (e.g., DSI, citizen participation, CHI) could scale up or inform regional adaptation planning.

7. Gjovik

Questions:

- /

Action points:

- /

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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